

ISic0980

I.Sicily inscription 0980

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κῆτε
2. Παῦλα ζήσιασ[α]
3. ἔτη κε· ἀλνέλυσεII
4. δὲ τὸν βίον πρὸ η καλ[αν]
5. δῶν Δεκενβρίων · τ [ὺ]πα(τία)
6. Ἰερίου καὶ ἌρδαβΙΟIIουρί[ου] τῶη[ν]
7. λαμπροτάτων

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492606

EDCS 39102133

PHI 140457

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0159 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 36.0875
Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos.* 28-29: 3-29. At 18 no.57

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0980. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340252>